

Occupational and residential exposures to organophosphate and pyrethroid pesticides in a rural setting

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Farmworker
Occupational exposure
Organophosphate pesticides
Pyrethroids
Personal protective equipment
Urinary metabolites
Rural area

ABSTRACT

Organophosphate (OP) and pyrethroid pesticides (PYR) are extensively used in agriculture, resulting in higher exposures among farmworkers. The present study reports the occurrence of 8 urinary OP and PYR metabolites in a sample of farmworkers and residents from Sucs ($n = 87$), a rural township in North West Catalonia (Spain). The aim of the present study was to examine differences in urinary pesticide metabolite concentrations between occupationally-exposed (farmworkers; $n = 45$) and environmentally-exposed subjects ($n = 42$) and to assess the relationship between pesticide's exposures and occupational activities in a real-case scenario.

Six OP and two PYR metabolites have been investigated, urine samples were extracted using SPE extraction and analyzed by UPLC-MS/MS. Three OP metabolites were commonly detectable in urine, namely TCPY (metabolite of chlorpyrifos), PNP (parathion) and DEAMPY (pirimiphos). Regarding pyrethroids, the two analyzed metabolites, 3-PBA and 4F-3-PBA, were detected in a high proportion of urine samples. Differences in concentrations between both groups were statistically significant for TCPY and 4F-3-PBA (Mann-Whitney U Test for independent groups, $p < 0.05$). In the case of TCPY, the concentrations were higher among the farmworkers, which is consistent with their occupational activity. The small differences found in DEAMPY, PNP, 3-PBA or even the significant higher concentrations of 4F-3-PBA among rural population suggest a general exposure to these compounds, even in those who do not carry an occupational activity.

Specific personal protective equipment (PPE) among farmworkers, such as the use of gloves and mask during mixing, showed a decrease in the exposure levels, although the differences were not statistically significant. However, a positive association was found between the use of a cap during mixing (for PNP and 3-PBA) and during application (only for 3-PBA). However, this piece of cloth is mainly used for sun protection, and when not cleaned after the handling of pesticides, it might represent a continuous source of exposure through dermal contact. Farmworkers using tractors with cabin had statistically significant lower concentrations of DEAMPY than those using a tractor without cabin. The previous results suggest that occupational protections should be encouraged among farmworkers and other potential workers handling with pesticides.

1. Introduction

Organophosphate (OP) and pyrethroid (PYR) pesticides are used in agriculture, gardening, domestic and veterinary applications. They were used as a replacement of organochlorine insecticides, due to the higher liability to environmental degradation of the latter. However, their extensive use has involved the occurrence of residues of these compounds in dietary products, water, outdoor and indoor air and house dust (Banerjee et al., 2012; Coscolla et al., 2017; Gibbs et al., 2017;

Mercier et al., 2011; Sousa et al., 2018; Tang et al., 2018), resulting in human exposure through diet (Fortes et al., 2013; Quijano et al., 2016; Tsatsakis et al., 2003), dermal contact or inhalation (Becker et al., 2006; McKone et al., 2007).

General exposure to OP pesticides among adults has been associated with cancer (Engel et al., 2017), deleterious impacts on the reproductive and endocrine systems (Jain, 2017) and diabetes (Starling et al., 2014). PYR pesticides have lower toxicity to mammals than OPs (Narahashi et al., 2007). However, in adults, exposures to these compounds have

Abbreviations: PPE, Personal Protective Equipment; OP, Organophosphate pesticide; PYR, Pyrethroid; LOD, Limit of detection; GM, Geometric mean; CI, Confidence interval; IQR, Interquartile range; BMI, Body mass index; UPLC, Ultra-Performance Liquid Chromatography.

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2022.114186>

Received 25 April 2022; Received in revised form 1 August 2022; Accepted 19 August 2022

Available online 27 August 2022

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been found to be significantly related to diabetes (Park et al., 2019), effects on the endocrine system (Santos et al., 2019) and depleted pulmonary function (Kim et al., 2019). Among exposed populations, especially people working and handling with pesticides, one of the most immediate toxic effects of OP pesticides is the inhibition of acetylcholinesterase causing neurotoxicity (Filippi et al., 2021), while the mechanism of action for PYR in the nervous system is through the interaction with sodium channels and the induction of prolonged depolarization in neural cells, making OPs more toxic for humans than PYR (Lucero and Muñoz-Quezada, 2021).

After entering into the body, OPs and PYRs are mostly metabolised by cytochrome P450 enzymes and the hydrolysis products excreted through the urine (Barr, 2008). The hydroxylated organic moieties generated from OP or PYR pesticides (Chambers and Carr, 1995; Mikata et al., 2012) allow for the identification of the precursor compound. The half-lives of most OP and PYR pesticides and their metabolites are in the order of a few hours to some months (Hoffmann and Papendorf, 2006; Li et al., 2019b). Repeated urine collection and analysis provide information on average exposures over long time periods (Li et al., 2019a). However, single-spot urine analyses can be used for comparative assessment of short-term environmental or dietary exposures between individuals when the samples are collected simultaneously (Bradman et al., 2013). Spot urine sample analysis is therefore the common procedure in human biomonitoring studies.

Farmworkers are one of the most exposed population groups to pesticides (Katsikantami et al., 2019), hence their assessment is necessary to protect their health and prevent high exposures. Previous studies have found pesticides in two of the main rivers of Catalonia; these pesticides come from the wide agricultural areas around the rivers (Masiá et al., 2015; Barbieri et al., 2021).

The current study is based on Sucs, a rural township in the North West of Catalonia (Spain), whose main economy is based on agriculture. Among their inhabitants (around 600 people), most of adult men are involved in activities related to agriculture, especially sweet fruit plantations, with direct handling of pesticides. Sucs is therefore considered a closed system, allowing a real-case study on the exposure to pesticides in both farmworkers and rural residents. The present study is therefore aimed to determine the concentrations of urinary pesticide metabolites in both occupationally-exposed individuals and people living in the rural setting. In addition, the study will deepen in the patterns of exposure among farmworkers during different occupational activities, including the handling of pesticides and the use of personal protective equipment (PPE). For this purpose, the current pilot study evaluated the impact of pesticide exposures in rural workers from Sucs. It is the first time this rural location is studied.

2. Methods

2.1. Population and study design

The study participants from both groups (farmworkers and rural residents) were recruited in Sucs (Lleida province, Catalonia; [Supplemental Figures S1 and S2](#)). A total of 45 farmers (occupationally-exposed men) and 42 rural residents from Sucs volunteered to participate. This represents around 20% of the adult population of the Sucs township, and therefore, it has great coverage in terms of representativeness. The inclusion criteria for participation was being over 18 years old. In addition, in the case of farmworkers, they must carry daily involvement in the fields and the application of pesticides.

Urine samples were collected during spring 2016 and stored at -20°C until analysis. A personal questionnaire with basic information (age, sex, weight, height and place of residence) and a written consent was filled out by each individual. An additional questionnaire administered only to occupationally exposed individuals recorded data concerning occupation, frequency of pesticide application, use and kind of tractor, as well as use of personal protection equipment, among others.

Another questionnaire was administered to the rural residents, asking them about specific activities with pesticides, local food consumption and place of work. The research of the study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the University of Oviedo (UO, Spain).

2.2. Sample preparation and instrumental analysis

Sample preparation and analytical procedures have been described elsewhere (Garí et al., 2018). Briefly, centrifuged and filtered urine samples and a mixture of isotopically labelled internal standards were introduced into 7-mL vials for their hydrolysis with β -glucuronidase. The hydrolysed samples were extracted using solid-phase extraction, cartridges were preconditioned with a mixture of MeOH:acetone followed by a solution of acetic acid 1% in H_2O . Pesticides' metabolites were eluted with a mixture of MeOH:acetone. Collected extracts were reduced to near dryness with a gentle N_2 stream and transferred to chromatographic vials with MeOH: H_2O .

Identification and quantification of six specific organophosphate metabolites and 2 pyrethroid metabolites was carried out using an Ultra-Performance Liquid Chromatography (UPLC Acquity H-Class, Waters, Milford, MA, USA) equipped with an electrospray ionization (ESI) interface. The chromatographic separation was performed on a Betasil C18 column. Specifically, for organophosphates, the following metabolites were analyzed: 2-diethylamino-6-methyl pyrimidin-4-ol (DEAMPY), 2-isopropyl-6-methyl-4-pyrimidol (IMPY), malathion dicarboxylic acid (MDA), 4-nitrophenol (PNP), 3-chloro-4methyl-7-hydroxycoumarin (CMHC) and 3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinol (TCPY), representing the organic moieties of pirimiphos, diazinon, malathion, parathion, coumaphos and chlorpyrifos, respectively ([Supplementary Table S1](#)). Concerning pyrethroids, one specific PYR metabolite, 4-fluoro-3-phenoxybenzoic acid (4-F-3-BPA), representing cyfluthrin, and 3-phenoxybenzoic acid (3-PBA), a metabolite of several PYRs, were analyzed ([Supplementary Table S1](#)).

Synthetic urine (Surine, Preserve Free, Sigma-Aldrich) was used for blanks, quality control (QC) materials and calibration curves. Accuracies were assessed at two levels, low and high, and calibration curves were prepared by adding 25 μL of standard solutions at concentrations ranging from 2.5 to 800 ppb into synthetic urine. Quantification was performed by isotopically-labelled internal standards (Garí et al., 2018). In addition, the methodology is externally checked out by participation in rounds of the German External Quality Assessment Scheme (G-Equas) since 2016, which includes the organophosphate metabolites PNP and TCPY and the pyrethroid metabolites 3-PBA and 4F-3-PBA.

2.3. Data analysis

Data analysis and graphics were performed using the statistical software R (R Development Core Team, 2022). Statistics was focused on the metabolites found above limit of detection in more than 35% of the samples: DEAMPY, PNP, TCPY, 3-PBA and 4F-3-PBA. Values under the LOD were replaced by one-half of the limit of detection. Geometric means (GM) and 95% confidence intervals (CI), as well as medians were used for descriptive analysis. Differences of OP and PYR between the population groups (farmworkers and rural residents) and their association with the use of personal protection equipment in the case of occupational exposures were evaluated using the Mann-Whitney *U* Test for independent samples. In addition, these results were also reported as medians and interquartile ranges (IQR).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Socio-demographic characteristics

[Table 1](#) summarizes the descriptive characteristics of the 87 volunteers included in this study. While all farmworkers were men, rural residents were mainly women (67%). The distribution of tasks in all

Table 1
Socio-demographic characteristics of the studied population, farmworkers (n = 45) and rural residents (n = 42).

Participants n (%)	Participants n (%)	P-value ^c
Farmworkers	Rural residents	
Age (n = 44)	Age (n = 42)	
52 ± 16	49 ± 16	
Gender (n = 45)	Gender (n = 42)	<0.001
Women	Women	28 (67)
Men	Men	14 (33)
BMI^a (kg/m²) (n = 45)	BMI^a (kg/m²) (n = 40)	0.68
Healthy	Healthy	17 (43)
Overweight	Overweight	15 (37)
Obese	Obese	8 (20)
Cultivation type (n = 44)	Activity with pesticides (n = 40)	
Fruit tree	Any	9 (22)
Kitchen garden	Cleaning working clothes	14 (35)
	Walk/Help	17 (43)
Cultivation area (n = 44)	Local product consumption (n = 42)	
≤20 ha	Yes	40 (95)
>20 ha	No	2 (5)
Treatment duration (n = 45)	Place of work (n = 41)	
≤20 days/year	Sucs	21 (51)
>20 days/year	Other place	20 (49)
Tools (n = 43)		
Tractor		
Hand pressure sprayer		
Hydraulic sprayer		
Tractor type (n = 35)		
With cabin		
Without cabin		
PPE^b during mixing (n = 44)		
Gloves		
Always/sometimes		
Never		
Nose-mouth mask		
Always/sometimes		
Never		
Cap		
Always/sometimes		
Never		
PPE^b during application (n = 44)		
Nose-mouth mask		
Always/sometimes		
Never		
Cap		
Always/sometimes		
Never		

^a BMI: Body mass index; healthy (18.5–25 kg/m²), overweight (25–30 kg/m²), obese (≥30 kg/m²).

^b PPE: Personal Protective Equipment.

^c P-value from Chi-square test, comparing gender and BMI between farmworkers and rural residents.

Sucs' farms was the same, men were the ones dedicated to the application of pesticides and daily involvement in the fields while women were the ones working on fruit packaging or other tasks which did not involve the direct use of pesticides. The average age of the participating farmworkers was 52 years old, and 49 years in the group of rural residents, with ages ranging 22–81 years and 17–77 years, respectively. According to BMI, 33% of farmworkers had a healthy weight, 45% were overweight and 22% obese. In rural residents, these percentages were 43%, 37% and 20%, respectively.

72% of the farmworkers' plantations were fruit tree, while the rest (28%) had a kitchen garden. Half of the farmworkers had a cultivation area bigger than 20 ha, 60% of them sprayed their cultivations more than 10 days/year and 82% used a tractor for spraying (being a tractor with cabin in 81% of these cases). Regarding PPE, their use was evaluated twice: during mixing and during application. During mixing, 47% of farmworkers always used gloves, 42% a cap, and only 29% a nose-mouth mask, while during application, 27% of the workers were always using nose-mouth mask and only 11% a cap. Individuals using the aforementioned PPEs, together with those using them sometimes were grouped together. Therefore, a higher percentage of farmers wore PPE during mixing, in relation to the use of it during application. This behaviour was reported in previous works, indicating that farmers are

aware of the risks to pesticides' exposures (Russell-Green et al., 2020).

Rural residents from Sucs were asked about local product consumption, activities related to pesticides and whether they work in Sucs itself or another place. Just 9 residents out of 40 performed an activity non-related with pesticides, 14 were in charge of the cleaning (e.g. clothes used for spraying), and 17 supported farmworkers or spent free time around the fields (e.g. walking or running). Almost all volunteers from Sucs (95%) consumed local products and half of them worked in Sucs, while the remaining residents worked in other locations.

3.2. Urinary concentrations in farmworkers and rural residents

Table 2 reports the concentrations of the analyzed metabolites in urine samples. Detection frequencies ranged from non-detected to 100% both in farmworkers and rural residents, being PNP and TCPY the most detected metabolites in both groups (100% for PNP and TCPY in farmworkers and 100% and 95% for rural residents, respectively).

The most abundant compound in both groups was TCPY, chlorpyrifos' metabolite, with median concentrations of 3.3 µg/g creatinine and 2.4 µg/g creatinine in farmworkers and rural residents, respectively, followed by 3-PBA among farmworkers (median 2.4 µg/g creatinine) and PNP in rural residents (median 1.8 µg/g creatinine). Despite the ban

Table 2

Non-adjusted (ng/mL) and creatinine adjusted ($\mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine) urinary levels of OP and PYR metabolites for farmworkers (non-adjusted $n = 45$; adjusted $n = 44$) and rural residents (non-adjusted $n = 42$; adjusted $n = 41$).

Metabolite	LOD ^a (ng/mL)	Farmworkers				Rural residents			
		DF ^b (%)	GM (CI) ^c	Median	Range	DF ^b (%)	GM (CI) ^c	Median	Range
Non-adjusted results									
DEAMPY	0.017	82	0.80 (0.40–1.6)	1.8	nd – 15.6	83	0.60 (0.29–1.3)	1.1	nd – 18.8
IMPY	0.014	2	<LD	<LD	nd – 14.2	5	<LD	<LD	nd – 13.7
MDA	0.069	0	<LD	<LD	<LD	0	<LD	<LD	<LD
PNP	0.017	100	2.6 (2.0–3.4)	2.3	0.25–16.0	100	1.5 (1.0–2.2)	1.8	0.070–14.4
TCPY	0.02	100	4.5 (3.7–5.4)	4.2	1.2–20.0	95	1.9 (1.2–3.0)	2.4	nd – 8.8
CMHC	0.026	0	<LD	<LD	<LD	0	<LD	<LD	<LD
3-PBA	0.018	91	1.7 (0.98–3.0)	2.4	nd – 20.5	86	0.87 (0.46–1.7)	1.6	nd – 15.0
4F-3-PBA	0.019	47	0.036 (0.023–0.055)	<LD	nd – 0.26	64	0.059 (0.038–0.092)	0.153	nd – 0.34
Creatinine adjusted results									
DEAMPY			0.58 (0.28–1.2)	1.2	nd – 11.2		0.56 (0.30–1.1)	0.87	nd – 9.2
IMPY			<LD	<LD	nd – 8.9		<LD	<LD	nd – 14.7
MDA			<LD	<LD	<LD		<LD	<LD	<LD
PNP			1.9 (1.5–2.5)	1.7	0.40–12.9		1.4 (1.1–1.8)	1.5	0.23–7.8
TCPY			3.2 (2.6–4.1)	3.3	0.71–16.7		1.8 (1.1–2.8)	2.4	nd – 20.1
CMHC			<LD	<LD	<LD		<LD	<LD	<LD
3-PBA			1.2 (0.68–2.2)	1.7	nd – 13.1		0.78 (0.41–1.5)	1.5	nd – 14.1
4F-3-PBA			0.027 (0.016–0.045)	<LD	nd – 0.49		0.058 (0.034–0.099)	0.11	nd – 1.4

^a LOD: Limit of detection.

^b DF: Detection frequency.

^c CI: Confidence Interval.

Fig. 1. Boxplots showing the distribution of OPs and PYR concentrations in farmworkers and rural residents ($\mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine).

of parathion by the European Commission since 2004, PNP is still being found in urine. Specifically, urinary PNP can also be found after exposure to nitrobenzene, a raw material for the production of several commercial items (e.g. aniline, solvents, lubricant oils, colorants, medicines, etc.), and a residue from motor vehicle fuels and smoking processes (Fernandez et al., 2020).

The concentrations of the studied metabolites were higher among farmworkers than those found in the inhabitants from Sucs, except 4F-3-PBA (Table 2; Fig. 1). These differences were statistically significant for TCPY (p -value = 0.032) and 4F-3-PBA (p -value = 0.024) (Mann-Whitney U Test for independent groups). In the case of TCPY, this is consistent with occupational activity (Wang et al., 2016; Ye et al., 2013). Farmworkers are directly exposed to pesticides through inhalation, dermal contact and indirect ingestion during mixing and application. An additional analysis has been performed in order to compare men workers with men residents (Supplemental Figure S3). Except for DEAMPY, the trends between farmworkers and rural residents taking into account all volunteers or only men are similar, and the differences between them are not statistically significant. In the case of DEAMPY,

although the differences are also not statistically significant, when considering only men, rural residents show higher concentrations than farmworkers (Supplemental Figure S3, right panel), while when considering all volunteers, there are practically no differences. This result suggest that exposure to pirimiphos (the parent compound of DEAMPY) might be different between women and men. In addition, when exploring the rural residents, there were a higher amount of men who reported an additional activity with pesticides, while among women, this was mainly related to cleaning clothes (data not shown). Therefore, it might be possible that men in the rural environment, although not being farmworkers, are probably in close contact with pesticides, sometimes even more than farmworkers themselves.

The small differences found in DEAMPY, PNP, 3-PBA or even the statistically significant higher concentrations of 4F-3-PBA among rural population indicate that even those who do not work with pesticides are exposed to them in their daily life. A closer look to the rural population (Table 1) showed that 77% of the volunteers had some connexion with pesticides (taking walks around the fields, helping in family farms or cleaning working clothes), and only 9 individuals out of 40 had no

Fig. 2. Boxplots showing the distribution of OPs and PYR concentrations in farmworkers and rural residents categorized by their relationship with pesticides ($\mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine).

relation with them. It can be seen that there are not evident differences between the four groups (Fig. 2), aside from the huge variability. A previous study from France also suggested that improper equipment cleaning at the end of application may be an important source of pesticide exposure (Baldi et al., 2006). These results suggest that in a small town like Sucs where the main economic activity is farming and the consumption of local products is common (95%), the population is exposed to pesticides through diet or inhalation, even in those individuals who do not have a direct relation with pesticides.

3.3. International comparison

The availability of studies reporting OP and PYR exposures among farmworkers or sprayers is very scarce. Compared to other studies performed in farmworkers, the concentrations in Sucs were similar to those found in North Carolina (US) for TCPY and 3-PBA (GM; $3.3 \mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine and $1.0 \mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine, respectively) (Arcury et al., 2016)

and Argentina (3-PBA GM; $2.3 \mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine) (Filippi et al., 2021) but lower than those reported in Shandong (China) (TCPY GM; $7.6 \mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine), Egypt (3-PBA median; $4.0 \mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine) and Argentina (DEAMPY GM; $5.3 \mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine) (Filippi et al., 2021; Singleton et al., 2014; Wang et al., 2016). The concentrations found in this study were higher than those found in Argentina for PNP and TCPY (PNP GM; $0.92 \mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine; TCPY GM; $0.20 \mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine) (Filippi et al., 2021). Rural residents have been widely studied, especially vulnerable population groups such as pregnant women or children. Compared to the current study, concentrations of PNP, TCPY and 3-PBA were similar than those found in Galicia (in another Spanish rural community), North Carolina (US) and California (US) (medians between 1.1 and $1.5 \mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine for PNP, between 2.4 and $3.4 \mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine for TCPY, and between 1.3 and $1.5 \mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine for 3-PBA). Results for DEAMPY and 3-PBA were higher in Sucs than in Galicia and North Carolina (for DEAMPY) and North Carolina and Poland (for 3-PBA) (Arcury et al., 2007; Garí et al., 2018; Trunnelle et al., 2014; Wielgomas and

Table 3
Median and IQR urinary concentration differences ($\mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine) of main metabolites detected by farmworkers' occupational determinants.

Determinants	DEAMPY		PNP		TCPY		3-PBA	
	Median	IQR ^a	Median	IQR ^a	Median	IQR ^a	Median	IQR ^a
Cultivation type								
Fruit tree (n = 34)	1.2	0.50–2.9	1.7	1.1–2.7	3.0	1.7–5.3	1.8	1.1–3.0
Kitchen garden (n = 10)	1.0	0.19–1.5	1.8	1.2–4.0	4.0	3.3–4.9	1.6	1.0–2.8
Cultivation area								
≤20 ha (n = 22)	1.2	0.58–2.0	1.6	1.2–3.5	3.5	1.8–5.4	2.3	1.3–3.8
>20 ha (n = 22)	1.1	0.42–2.9	1.8	1.1–2.2	3.1	1.8–4.3	1.4	0.99–2.8
Tools								
Tractor (n = 35)	1.3	0.60–2.6	1.7	1.2–2.6	3.1	1.6–4.7	1.4	1.1–3.4
Other ^b (n = 9)	0.77	0.019–1.3	1.3	1.2–2.4	4.0	3.2–6.2	2.0	1.6–2.4
Tractor type								
With cabin (n = 28)	1.1 ^c	0.47–2.2	1.6	1.1–2.1	3.3	1.7–4.8	1.4	1.0–3.2
Without cabin (n = 7)	2.5 ^c	1.4–7.0	5.4	1.6–6.6	2.9	2.1–4.1	1.9	1.5–4.4
Treatment duration								
≤20 days/year (n = 25)	1.3	0.77–3.0	1.7	1.2–2.8	3.8	1.7–6.9	2.3	1.0–3.0
>20 days/year (n = 19)	0.77	0.013–2.0	1.5	1.1–2.9	3.1	1.8–3.8	1.4	0.98–2.7

^a IQR: Interquartile range.

^b Hand pressure sprayer and hydraulic sprayer have been grouped as other.

^c p-value < 0.05 Mann-Whitney U Test.

Table 4Median urinary concentration differences ($\mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine) of main metabolites detected by the use of personal protection equipment.

PPE	DEAMPY		PNP		TCPY		3-PBA	
	Median	IQR ^a						
During mixing								
Gloves								
Always/sometimes (n = 30)	0.92	0.42–2.0	1.3	1.1–2.3	2.7	1.5–4.5	1.5	1.1–2.9
Never (n = 14)	1.6	1.0–6.4	2.0	1.8–4.3	3.8	3.2–6.8	2.3	1.1–3.0
Nose-mouth mask								
Always/sometimes (n = 24)	0.92	0.31–2.60	1.3	1.1–2.6	2.7	1.5–4.2	1.6	1.3–3.10
Never (n = 20)	1.4	0.55–2.5	2.0	1.6–3.0	3.9	2.5–6.8	2.5	0.96–3.0
Cap								
Always/sometimes (n = 22)	1.5	0.88–3.3	2.0	1.3–5.2	3.0	1.5–4.7	2.1	1.3–3.0
Never (n = 22)	0.70	0.42–1.6	1.5	1.1–2.0	3.6	1.9–5.4	1.3	0.85–3.0
During application								
Nose-mouth mask								
Always/sometimes (n = 9)	1.1	0.84–3.4	2.3	1.2–5.4	3.1	1.7–6.9	1.7	1.6–2.4
Never (n = 35)	1.2	0.44–2.3	1.6	1.2–2.3	3.4	1.8–4.9	1.4	1.0–3.0
Cap								
Always/sometimes (n = 14)	1.4	0.88–3.1	1.7	1.2–5.2	3.0	1.8–4.6	2.3	1.4–3.7
Never (n = 30)	1.1	0.42–2.4	1.7	1.1–2.2	3.6	1.8–5.4	1.4	0.94–2.8

^a IQR: Interquartile range; ²Hand pressure sprayer and hydraulic sprayer have been grouped as other.

Piskunowicz, 2013).

3.4. Influence of occupational factors and use of PPE

Use of PPE is considered the last safety shield and one of the most important mechanisms used by workers to reduce chemical hazards. In the agricultural field, PPE is specially needed during application and spraying (Sookhtanlou and Allahyari, 2021). This is of special importance in the current study, since some of the farmworkers mentioned that after pesticide application in the fields, they usually experienced headache, even after using PPEs.

Different farmworkers' occupational characteristics that may influence de urinary OP and PYR pesticide concentrations have been evaluated, including the use of PPE during mixing and application of pesticides (Tables 3 and 4). In both tables, the assessed variables have been grouped into 2 categories, median differences have been evaluated using the Mann-Whitney *U* Test, and the comparisons are reported as median values and IQRs. Farmworkers showed no statistically significant differences with respect to cultivation type, cultivation area, tools or treatment duration (days/year) with pesticides. The only statistically significant association relied on DEAMPY when using a tractor with cabin or without it. Farmworkers who used a tractor with cabin had lower DEAMPY levels than those who used a tractor without cabin (1.1 $\mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine vs. 2.5 $\mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine; *p*-value = 0.043; Table 3). Only 7 out of 35 farmworkers used a tractor without cabin, and 3 of them did not use a mask during the application of pesticides (data not shown). Use of personal protective equipment such as gloves, nose-mouth masks or caps is essential when manipulating pesticides. In general, in the case of gloves and masks, farmworkers who never used them during mixing had higher concentrations than those who always or sometimes used these PPE (Table 4), although the differences between the two groups were not statistically significant. As it has been mentioned before, the majority of workers (81%) used a tractor during the application of pesticides, hence being less exposed to these compounds than during mixing. In addition, most of them never used the mask (80%) in front of the 20% who always or sometimes used it. These differences make the two studied groups non-homogenous, and the obtained results contain a high variability. Concerning the use of cap, the general trend is the opposite, finding higher concentrations in those individuals who always or sometimes used caps, either in mixing or during application. Unlike gloves and masks, caps are specially used for sun protection, and if this piece of cloth is not well cleaned after the manipulation of the products, it may represent a continuous source of exposure, through dermal contact.

3.5. Strengths and limitations

The present study of OPs and PYR in rural population uses a robust analytical methodology published in 2018 (Garí et al., 2018). Since then, this methodology has been employed in other population studies from Spain, Italy, Slovenia and Argentina (Bravo, 2019, 2020a,b; Filippi et al., 2021). In addition, this is one of the few study cases where most of the inhabitants of a town are in direct contact with pesticides, either working or doing other related-activities. On the other hand, this study is based on a relatively small sample size. Although occupational studies are sometimes based on a reduced number of individuals, in the present study we were able to include 44 workers. In addition, the fact that all farmworkers were men might have introduced some bias into the statistical analysis. In any case, pesticides' exposure is not commonly related to gender, and previous studies focused on occupational populations have already faced this problem (Filippi et al., 2021). And finally, we would like to mention that in the current study we have not addressed the simultaneous exposures to organophosphate and pyrethroids, and their metabolic implications in workers. There are many other pesticide groups, and the improvement of analytical methods to analyze further compounds are needed.

4. Conclusions

Three metabolites of organophosphate pesticides (DEAMPY, PNP and TCPY) and the two analyzed metabolites for pyrethroids (3-PBA and 4F-3-PBA) were commonly detected in urine samples of farmworkers and rural residents from Sucs. The most abundant in both groups was TCPY, followed by 3-PBA in farmworkers and PNP in rural residents. Farmworkers had higher concentrations of TCPY but lower concentrations of 4F-3-PBA than rural residents from Sucs, both with statistically significant results. The other compounds showed non-statistically significant differences between the two population groups. In any case, the concentrations found among rural residents suggest that even those individuals not working or handling pesticides are exposed to them in their daily life. Personal protective equipment such as gloves and masks during mixing or application of pesticides has been shown to decrease the overall exposure. Farmworkers using tractors with cabins had lower DEAMPY levels than those using tractors without cabins, with statistically significant results. On the other hand, the continuous use of a cap (mostly intended for sun protection) increases the exposure to OP and PYR, suggesting that not cleaning this piece of cloth assiduously may lead to a continuous dermal exposure. The previous results suggest that occupational protections should be encouraged among farmworkers and

other potential workers handling pesticides. Further research is needed in order to assess in more detail the implications of personal protective equipment, specially regarding the use and handling of pesticides in the agricultural framework.

Credit author statement

NB performed the statistical analyses, interpreted the results and wrote the paper. MG developed the analytical methodology, interpreted the results and contributed to sample analysis, statistical methods and paper writing. JOG designed the study, organized the sampling, interpreted the results and contributed to paper writing. All authors discussed the health implications of the results.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

Acknowledgements

The authors are grateful to the inhabitants of Sucs who participated in this study. Financial support from the European Union Projects EDCMET (H2020-HEALTH/0490–825762) and PARC (HLTH-2021-ENVHALTH-3:101057014) are acknowledged. MG acknowledges the support from the Joachim Herz Foundation through the Add-on Fellowship for Interdisciplinary Science and the IDAEA-CSIC Severo Ochoa Excellence Programme through the Grant CEX 2018-000894-S funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2022.114186>.

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